

Polarographic Study of L-4-Hydroxyproline Complexes of Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II)

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Manuscript received 19 October 1981, revised 2 July 1982, accepted 25 August 1982

Polarographic behaviour of Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) has been studied in the presence of increasing concentrations of L-4-hydroxyproline (LHP) at a constant ionic strength $\mu = 0.1$ (NaClO_4) and at constant pH. Zn(II) yields a single quasi-reversible wave at $[\text{LHP}] \leq 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol l}^{-1}$ but an irreversible wave at higher $[\text{LHP}] \leq 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol l}^{-1}$. Co(II) yields a single irreversible wave but in the case of Ni(II), at the lower $[\text{LHP}] \leq 8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol l}^{-1}$ two irreversible waves appear, while at higher $[\text{LHP}] \geq 1 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol l}^{-1}$ the first wave disappears and only the more negative one persists. In each case the waves are diffusion-controlled. Zn(II) and Ni(II) form three successive complexes, viz., $[\text{Zn}(\text{LHP})]^+$, $[\text{Zn}(\text{LHP})_2]$, $[\text{Zn}(\text{LHP})_3]^-$; $[\text{Ni}(\text{LHP})]^+$, $[\text{Ni}(\text{LHP})_2]$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{LHP})_3]^-$ with $\log \beta_1 = 5.3$, $\log \beta_2 = 10.3$, $\log \beta_3 = 16.9$ and $\log \beta_1 = 12.0$, $\log \beta_2 = 15.7$ and $\log \beta_3 = 18.2$, respectively. Co(II) forms a single complex $[\text{Co}(\text{LHP})_2]$ with $\log \beta = 9.62$.

HAQ and Khan¹ found the polarographic reduction of Cu(II)-L-hydroxyproline system irreversible and determined the composition and dissociation constant of Cu(II)-L-hydroxyproline complex. Kabir-ud-Din and Khan² studied similarly the interaction of $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ with L-proline and reported two successive complex species of $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$. Gaur and coworkers³ studied the Zn(II)-L-hydroxyproline system polarographically at $\mu = 0.5$ (NaClO_4) and reported two successive complexes with stability constants $\beta_1 = 30$ and $\beta_2 = 3.5 \times 10^8$. A critical examination of the latter work, however, reveals that the role of pH in complex formation was not taken into consideration. Their calculation of stability constants also suffers from the serious error in that they did not take into consideration the free ligand concentration (hydroxyproline ion concentration) in the calculations. A survey of literature reveals that Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes with hydroxyproline have not been studied polarographically so far. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to study the polarographic behaviour of Zn(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) in the presence of increasing concentrations of L-hydroxyproline for the determination of composition and stability constants of the complexes formed.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A. R. grade and their stock solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The concentration of Ni(II) and Co(II) was kept at $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol l}^{-1}$ in each case while that of Zn(II) was kept at $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol l}^{-1}$. NaClO_4 solution was used to keep the ionic strength constant ($\mu = 0.1$). The concentration of hydroxyproline ion was calculated⁴⁻⁶ from pH of the solution and pK values of L-4-hydroxyproline ($\text{pK}_1 = 1.18$ and $\text{pK}_2 = 9.66$). Triton X-100 ($1 \times 10^{-3}\%$)

was used as maxima suppressor in the cases of Ni(II) and Co(II) while for Zn(II), it was not required as there was no maximum. Polarograms of the solutions were taken at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with a manual set-up (Toshniwal polarograph, Model CLO2 in conjunction with a Toshniwal polyflex galvanometer, Model PL 50). Purified nitrogen was used to remove dissolved oxygen, and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) was used as the reference electrode. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M NaClO_4 , open circuit): $m = 2.46 \text{ mg/sec}$, $t = 2.44 \text{ sec}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.11 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/3}$, $h_{\text{corr}} = 61.8 \text{ cm}$. The number of electrons (n) involved in the reduction process of each system was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon⁶. This gave the value of $n = 2$ in each case.

Results and Discussion

(a) *Zn(II)-L-4-hydroxyproline (LHP) system*: Polarograms of solutions containing $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol l}^{-1}$ Zn(II) and $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol l}^{-1}$ LHP at different pH values showed maximum negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ at pH 6 and hence this pH was chosen for studying the complex formation. The concentration of LHP was varied from 0 to 0.1 mol l^{-1} and the corresponding concentrations of hydroxyproline ion $[\text{X}^-]$ were calculated (Table 1). In each case a single well-defined and diffusion-controlled quasi-reversible wave was obtained at lower concentrations of LHP ($\leq 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol l}^{-1}$), while at higher concentration ($\geq 4 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol l}^{-1}$) it was totally irreversible. Lal and Christian⁷ and recently Zutshi and Gupta⁸ have used a method for determining the stability constants of consecutively formed complex species that undergo irreversible reduction at d.m.e. This consists of determining the

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_1[X^-]$ FUNCTIONS OF Zn(II)-L-4-HYDROXYPROLINE SYSTEM

[LHP] $\times 10^3$ mol l ⁻¹	[X ⁻] $\times 10^4$ mol l ⁻¹	i_d μA	Slope mV	$-E_{1/2}$ V (SCE)	$-E_{1/2}$ V (SCE)	$F_0[X^-]$	$F_1[X^-]$ $\times 10^{-3}$	$F_2[X^-]$ $\times 10^{-12}$	$F_3[X^-]$ $\times 10^{-16}$
0	0	3.87	40	1.140	1.120	—	—	—	—
10	1.09	3.96	47	1.150	1.134	1.33	0.31	—	—
20	2.18	3.69	56	1.160	1.140	5.00	1.82	—	—
40	4.35	3.52	75	1.170	1.150	11.40	2.99	0.50	11.07
60	6.10	3.26	70	1.180	1.155	20.00	2.11	0.48	7.54
80	8.71	3.26	75	1.190	1.173	74.13	8.89	0.94	10.56
100	10.89	2.46	72	1.200	1.180	168.70	15.40	1.40	12.67

value of reversible half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}^r$) by Gellings' method⁹. This method has been followed in the present study and the $E_{1/2}^r$ values as a function of [hydroxyproline⁻] have been presented in Table 1.

A plot of $E_{1/2}^r$ vs $\log [X^-]$ is a smooth curve showing the formation of successive complexes. The method of DeFord and Hume¹⁰ modified by Irving¹¹ has been applied to determine the composition and stability constants of the complexes. The values of $F_1[X^-]$ functions have been determined and presented in Table 1. Zn(II) forms three successive complex species, viz., $[Zn(LHP)]^+$, $[Zn(LHP)_2]$ and $[Zn(LHP)_3]^-$ with $\log \beta_1 = 5.3$, $\log \beta_2 = 10.3$ and $\log \beta_3 = 16.9$, respectively.

(b) *Ni(II)-L-4-hydroxyproline (LHP) system*: Polarograms of solutions containing 1×10^{-2} mol l⁻¹ Ni(II) and 1×10^{-2} mol l⁻¹ LHP showed maximum negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ at pH 8 and hence this pH was chosen for studying the complex formation. In the absence of LHP, a single well-defined diffusion-controlled and irreversible wave is obtained. However, in presence of 1×10^{-2} mol l⁻¹ LHP, two well-defined waves appear which are diffusion-controlled and irreversible. $E_{1/2}$ of the first wave corresponds to the aquo-nickel ion and that of the second more negative wave corresponds to some complex species of Ni(II) with LHP. On further increasing the concentration (2×10^{-2} – 8×10^{-2} mol l⁻¹) of LHP the height of the first wave decreases while that of the second one increases due to complex formation. At still higher concentration (10^{-2} mole l⁻¹) of LHP the first wave disappears and only the more negative second wave persists whose $E_{1/2}$ is now shifted to more negative potentials (Table 2). On increasing the concentration of LHP beyond 10^{-2} mol l⁻¹, the $E_{1/2}$ of this wave records a further negative shift. The fact that $E_{1/2}$ of second wave changes from -1.22 V (up to 8×10^{-2} mole l⁻¹ LHP) to -1.27 V (at 10^{-2} mol l⁻¹ LHP) and then to 1.37 V (at LHP concentration $\geq 4 \times 10^{-2}$ mol l⁻¹) clearly shows the presence of complex species. This is borne out by the smooth curve of $E_{1/2}^r$ vs $\log [hydroxyproline^-]$. The method of DeFord and Hume modified by Irving has been used to determine the value of $F_1[X^-]$ functions at different $[X^-]$ (Table 3). Three complex species,

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF Ni(II)-L-4-HYDROXYPROLINE SYSTEM

[LHP] $\times 10^3$ mol l ⁻¹	First wave			Second wave			Slope (mV)	
	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (SCE)	i_d μA	$-E_{1/2}$ V (SCE)	$-E_{1/2}$ V (SCE)	First wave	Second wave	
0	6.68	0.97	—	—	0.96	80	—	
1	6.60	0.94	2.81	1.22	—	75	70	
2	2.90	0.93	5.28	1.22	—	75	73	
4	1.14	0.95	6.51	1.22	—	75	80	
6	0.61	0.95	6.42	1.22	—	73	80	
8	0.53	0.95	6.60	1.22	—	72	85	
10	—	—	6.95	1.270	1.22	—	90	
20	—	—	6.86	1.340	1.24	—	95	
40	—	—	6.34	1.365	1.26	—	95	
60	—	—	5.98	1.370	1.27	—	96	
80	—	—	5.81	1.372	1.30	—	95	
100	—	—	5.80	1.374	1.31	—	98	

viz., $[Ni(LHP)]^+$, $[Ni(LHP)_2]$ and $[Ni(LHP)_3]^-$ with $\log \beta_1 = 12.0$, $\log \beta_2 = 15.7$ and $\log \beta_3 = 18.2$, respectively are formed.

 TABLE 3—VALUES OF $F_1[X^-]$ FUNCTIONS OF Ni(II)-L-4-HYDROXYPROLINE SYSTEM

[X ⁻] $\times 10^4$ mol l ⁻¹	$F_0[X^-]$ $\times 10^{-3}$	$F_1[X^-]$ $\times 10^{-12}$	$F_2[X^-]$ $\times 10^{-16}$	$F_3[X^-]$ $\times 10^{-20}$
0	—	—	—	—
2.18	6.55	2.55	0.71	0.097
4.36	31.55	7.01	1.38	0.202
8.77	162.40	18.52	2.01	0.173
13.07	386.39	29.53	2.18	0.130
15.24	1199.00	78.60	5.15	—
17.42	8471.30	486.15	22.84	—

(c) *Co(II)-L-4-hydroxyproline (LHP) system*: Polarograms of solutions containing 1×10^{-2} mol l⁻¹ Co(II) and 10^{-2} mol l⁻¹ LHP at different pH values exhibited maximum negative shift in $E_{1/2}$ at pH 8 and hence this pH was chosen for studying complex formation. The concentration of the ligand was varied from 1×10^{-2} to 4×10^{-2} mol l⁻¹ and the corresponding concentrations of hydroxyproline ion $[X^-]$ were calculated from the pH and pK values of LHP. In each case a single well-defined diffusion-controlled irreversible wave appeared with the $E_{1/2}$ shifting towards more negative potentials with increasing ligand concentration (Table 4). A plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log [X^-]$ was a straight line showing the formation of a single complex. The composition and stability constant of the complex

TABLE 4—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF
Co(II)-L-4-HYDROXYPROLINE SYSTEM

[LHP] ²⁺ × 10 ² mol l ⁻¹	[X ⁻] × 10 ⁴ mol l ⁻¹	i _d μA	-E _{1/2} V (SCE)	Slope mV	D × 10 ⁶ cm ² s ⁻¹
0	0	5.72	1.38	110	3.6
1	2.39	5.28	1.40	100	3.1
2	4.35	5.28	1.45	106	3.1
3	6.55	5.10	1.47	110	2.9
4	8.71	5.02	1.49	111	2.8
6	10.96	4.22	1.53	110	2.0
7	15.38	3.87	1.54	118	1.6
10	21.88	3.69	1.57	115	1.5
20	43.55	3.08	1.58	116	1.0
40	87.10	3.08	1.58	115	1.0

have been determined by the method of Tamamushi and Tanaka¹¹. The value of coordination number, j, comes out to be 2. The composition of the complex is, therefore, [Co(LHP)₂] with log β = 9.62.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. S. N. Srivastava, Principal, Agra College, Agra for necessary facilities.

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